

Study of corrosion kinetics a new voltammetric approach

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In the present study, the variation of metal corrodibility, solution corrosiveness and corrosion rates for carbon steel in 2 N H₂SO₄ solution as a function of time have been studied using gravimetric (planned interval test) and electrochemical methods. A new voltammetric method has been developed to determine the corrosion rates at short time intervals. The results of the corrosion of carbon steel in 2 N H₂SO₄ with and without polyvinyl pyrrolidone (PVP) and PVP + CaSO₄ inhibitor at short time intervals have been reported. It has also been possible to determine simultaneously the corrosion rates with respect to Fe^{II} and Fe^{III}.

Several corrosive media in which acids are the more dangerous¹ corroded carbon steel. The effect of polymers on the corrosion rate of iron and its alloys in acid solutions has been a subject of many investigators². The inhibitive action of polyvinyl pyrrolidone (PVP) towards the corrosion of carbon steel in 2 N H₂SO₄ solutions has been investigated. The corrosion and inhibition processes were examined at 25° by gravimetric (planned interval test (PIT) method) and some electrochemical viz. galvanostatic and potentiodynamic polarization measurements and polarographic and voltammetric methods.

The above mentioned methods prevalent in the field of corrosion rate determination, furnish only an average value for a long time interval³. However, looking at the sensitivity and minimum detection limits⁴ of voltammetric and polarographic techniques, we have developed polarographic and voltammetric i.e. differential pulse polarographic (DPP)

and differential pulse anodic stripping voltammetric (DPASV) procedures for the determinations of corrosion rates at short time intervals, the results of which have also been discussed in the paper.

Results and discussion

Weight loss determinations by gravimetry are shown as corrosion rates in the presence and absence of PVP inhibitor in Table 1. PVP decreases the corrosion rate by about 71% while in presence of PVP + CaSO₄ it decreased by about 95% after 24 h. The data obtained for the periods A₁ and B suggest that solution corrosiveness increases in the test solution (2 N H₂SO₄), while in the presence of PVP and PVP + CaSO₄ it decreases (B < A₁). The higher corrodibility of the solution can be attributed to the increase in concentration of Fe(II and III) ions in the solution. PVP molecules reduce the stimulating effect of Fe^{II} and Fe^{III}

Table 1. Corrosion rates of carbon steel in 2 N H₂SO₄ by gravimetric PIT measurements with and without inhibitors

Exposure time	Weight-loss (mg × 10 ²)		Corrosion rate Corrosion rate × 10 ⁴ in (mg cm ⁻² h ⁻¹)			Inhibition efficiency %	
	Without inhib.	With PVP PVP + CaSO ₄	Without inhib	PVP PVP + CaSO ₄	PVP	PVP + CaSO ₄ %	
A ₁ (3 h)	21.37	10.71 6.05	23.90	11.98 6.76	50	71	
A ₁ (24 h)	39.72	11.45 12.48	5.55	1.60 0.20	71	96	
A ₁ + I (24 + 3) h	42.96	15.92 14.48	5.33	1.33 0.15	75	97	
B (3 h)	3.19	1.30 8.76	3.56	1.46 0.98	58	72	
A _c (27-24) h	3.24	5.20 2.20	3.62	0.50 0.02	86	99	

*Concentration in (mg × 10²). **Corrosion rate × 10⁴ in (mg cm⁻² h⁻¹).

ions⁵. Metal corrodibility decreases ($A_c < B$) as a function of time in the presence of PVP and PVP + Ca. The formation of an inhibitor film requires some time, i.e. the inhibition process has an induction period. The increased inhibition effect of PVP + Ca may be understood on the basis of complex formation between metal ions coming out in the solution with PVP and also the formation of complexed film at metal surface.

Voltammetric measurements : The half wave potential ($E_{1/2}$)/peak potential (E_p) values for Fe^{II} and Fe^{III} are 0.81/0.83 V and 1.23/1.25 V, respectively, in DCP/DPP mode and E_p values are -0.4 V and -0.72 V for Fe^{II} and Fe^{III} in DPASV mode⁶ in 0.1 M ammonium tartrate and 0.001% gelatin at pH 9.0 ± 0.1 . Fig. 1 shows the DPASV voltammograms of corrosion mixtures of carbon steel at different time intervals. These curves show that using voltammetric and polarographic methods it is possible to analyse the presence of Fe^{II} and Fe^{III} in the solution simultaneously. Fe^{II} and Fe^{III} produce two separate well defined polarographic peaks in each case. The peak height (i_p) for Fe^{II} and Fe^{III} over the whole of the working concentration range in DCP, DPP and DPASV modes is proportional to their respective concentrations. The corrosion rates at different time intervals with respect to Fe^{II} and Fe^{III} are reported in Table 2. Fig. 2 shows the DPASV curves for the corrosion mixture to which 140 mg/l PVP has been added.

Since the shift in peak potential of Fe^{III} is more than that of Fe^{II}, in the complexed system, it can be concluded

Fig. 1. Differential pulse anodic stripping voltammogram of the corrosion solution of carbon steel in 2 N H₂SO₄ at different time intervals in 0.1 M ammonium tartrate + 0.001% gelatin at pH (9.0 ± 0.1).

Table 2. Corrosion rates with respect to concentrations Fe^{II} and Fe^{III} and total Fe for carbon steel in 2 N H₂SO₄ without inhibitor using voltammetric methods

Time	For Fe ^{II}		For Fe ^{III}		Total Fe	
	Conc. × 10 ² mg	C.R. × 10 ⁴ , mg cm ² h ⁻¹	Conc. × 10 ² mg	C.R. × 10 ⁴ , mg cm ² h ⁻¹	Conc. × 10 ² mg	C.R. × 10 ⁴ , mg cm ² h ⁻¹
DPASV mode						
5 min	3.18	12.80	1.98	7.97	5.16	20.77
10 min	3.34	6.72	2.10	4.22	5.44	10.95
20 min	3.39	3.41	5.37	5.40	8.76	8.81
1 h	3.31	1.11	6.05	2.01	9.36	3.14
2 h	5.09	0.85	11.83	1.98	16.92	2.83
24 h	8.22	0.11	24.09	0.33	32.31	0.45
DPP mode						
5 min	2.50	10.06	2.54	10.22	5.04	20.29
10 min	2.68	5.39	2.64	5.31	5.32	10.71
20 min	5.27	5.30	3.33	3.35	8.60	8.65
1 h	5.27	1.76	4.45	1.49	9.72	3.26
2 h	7.34	1.23	9.87	1.65	17.21	2.88
24 h	15.79	0.22	17.07	0.23	32.86	0.45

Fig. 2. Differential pulse anodic stripping voltammogram of the corrosion solution of carbon steel in 0.1 M ammonium tartrate + 0.001% gelatin at pH 9.0 ± 0.1 at different time intervals in presence of PVP inhibitor.

that Fe^{III} is more reactive in complex formation with PVP than Fe^{II}⁷. The corrosion rates in the presence of PVP and PVP + Ca have been tabulated in Table 3. A perusal of the data in Tables 2 and 3 clearly show that the rate of corro-

Table 3. Corrosion rates with respect to [Fe^{II} + Fe^{III}] for carbon steel in 2 N H₂SO₄ with PVP (140 mg/l) and PVP + CaSO₄ (140 + 50 mg/l) inhibitor

Time	With PVP			With PVP + CaSO ₄		
	Conc.*	C.R.**	% Inhibition	Conc.*	C.R.**	% Inhibition
5 min	4.02	16.30	44.7	3.50	14.20	51.1
10 min	5.87	1.91	47.5	4.26	10.10	55.5
20 min	6.25	6.31	48.7	4.96	4.30	65.0
1 h	6.84	2.30	49.1	5.10	1.42	68.8
2 h	12.13	1.71	50.1	5.96	1.00	70.5
24 h	15.31	0.11	71.2	11.41	0.03	95.1

*Concentration in (mg × 10²). **Corrosion rate × 10⁴ in (mg cm⁻² h⁻¹).

sion is very fast in the beginning of the experiment, and goes on decreasing with time. The corrosion inhibition efficiency of PVP is 71% and PVP + Ca is 95% after 24 h. A comparison of the corrosion rate data as calculated by voltammetric and weight loss methods clearly shows the utility of PVP + Ca as an inhibitor for the corrosion.

Synergistic effect of calcium : The synergistic effect of PVP + Ca on the inhibition of corrosion of carbon steel in acidic (2 N H₂SO₄) environment has been evaluated by above all methods. For corrosion of carbon steel in 2 N H₂SO₄, PVP inhibitor show only 44, 47, 48, 49, 50 and 71% after 5 min, 10 min, 20 min, 1 h, 2 h and 24 h. It is interesting to note that the inhibitor consisting of 55 mg/l CaSO₄ has 51, 55, 65, 69, 70 and 95% inhibition efficiency after above mentioned time interval. The mechanistic aspects of corrosion inhibition have been studied, based on the results obtained from gravimetric and some electrochemical methods, it is observed that the protective film consists of Fe^{II}-PVP complex, Fe^{III}-PVP complex and CaSO₄.

Conclusion :

DPP furnishes dependable data for corrosion rates with respect to Fe^{II} and Fe^{III} for the corrosion of carbon steel in acidic medium. Although gravimetric, galvanostatic, potentiodynamic and other methods are also in use for corrosion rate determination^{8,9}, but they furnish an average value of corrosion rate for a long span of time. However, the proposed voltammetric procedure is found to be highly useful for the determination of corrosion rates at short time intervals and that too with respect to different species present in the solution e.g. Fe^{II} and Fe^{III} in the present case, which is otherwise not possible using methods prevalent in the field of corrosion rate determination¹⁰ and also in the field of trace analysis e.g. atomic absorption spectrometry.

The proposed voltammetric procedure is found to be highly useful for the determination of corrosion rates at short time intervals with respect to different species present in the solution, e.g. Fe^{II} and Fe^{III} in the present case, which is not possible using other corrosion methods¹¹.

Experimental

Chemicals and reagents : All the chemicals used were of analar/B.D.H. grade, except for the inhibitor PVP which was of Loba, Mumbai.

Gravimetric measurements : The gravimetric measurements were carried out in 2 N H₂SO₄ solution.

Carbon steel specimens (50 × 20 × 4 mm, C - 0.23%, P - 0.05%, S - 0.05%) were used in the weight loss measurements. These specimens were polished following the usual

procedure⁹. The variations of metal corrodibility, solution corrosiveness and corrosion rate as a function of time were investigated with the PIT technique¹². After the experiments, the specimens were cleaned with water and acetone, weighed and from weight loss measurements, the corrosion rates were calculated. Similar experiment was done in the presence of 140 mg/l PVP and 140 mg/l PVP + 55 mg/l calcium sulphate inhibitors.

Voltammetric measurements : An Elico (India), pulse polarograph (model CL-90) was used for voltammetric studies. A cell consisting of three electrodes, viz. saturated calomel as reference electrode, a coiled platinum electrode as auxiliary and a dropping mercury electrode (for DPP) and glassy carbon fibre electrode (for DPASV) as working electrode, were used, respectively. The pulse amplitude used for DPP and DPASV measurement was 25 mV. The test specimens were polished as discussed earlier and one such specimen was suspended in one litre 2 N H₂SO₄ solution at RT (25 ± 1°). Nitrogen gas was bubbled through the solution throughout the experiment to avoid the oxidation of dissolved Fe^{II} to Fe^{III}. A definite aliquot of the solution was withdrawn from the test solution at short time intervals (5 min, 10 min, 20 min, 1 h, 2 h and 24 h) and polarograms and voltammograms were recorded in deaerated 0.1 M ammonium tartrate + 0.001% gelatin at pH 9.0 ± 0.02. The pH of the analyte was adjusted using ammonia solution. A similar experiment was performed using 140 mg/l PVP and

140 mg/l PVP + 55 mg/l Ca in one litre 2 N H₂SO₄ solution.

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